

A HERMENEUTIC INQUIRY INTO THE MENTAL HEALTH EXPERIENCE AMONG MALE STUDENTS: A MIXED METHOD APPROACH

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A Hermeneutic Inquiry into the Mental Health Experience Among Male Students: A Mixed Method Approach

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Abstract

Mental health is crucial throughout life and significantly influences overall well-being, yet it is often overlooked and stigmatized. Mental health issues among men are a significant public health concern due to societal norms that discourage emotional vulnerability and seeking help, leading to underreporting and inadequate access to necessary services. While research has explored these connections, a gap exists in understanding how these factors influence the mental health of young men specifically. The study was conducted in the college department of an institution in Malaybalay City, Bukidnon. It utilized an explanatory sequential research design, beginning with quantitative data collection to measure 106 male students' experiences with mental health expression and stigma, followed by qualitative methods to explore the experiences of 5 male students in-depth regarding their mental health expression. This study examines the factors influencing male students' willingness to communicate mental health expression. The study shows a strong positive correlation between adverse experiences and higher-level stigma, underscoring how societal attitudes discourage open communication. Moreover, the qualitative findings reveal that societal norms, personal experiences, and coping mechanisms play a role. Themes like stereotyping, social anxieties, and feelings of isolation emerged, highlighting students' challenges in seeking support. These qualitative insights support the quantitative data, which shows a high prevalence of stigma surrounding mental health. The study emphasizes the need to address these cultural and structural barriers to create a more supportive environment that reduces stigma and encourages help-seeking behavior among male students.

Keywords: *mental health, mental health expression, stigma*

Introduction

Mental health significantly influences overall well-being, encompassing emotional, psychological, and social aspects that influence how individuals think, feel, and act (Cleofas, 2020). It determines how people handle stress, relate to others, and make choices, affecting every stage of life from childhood and adolescence through adulthood. Mental health can influence personal and professional well-being, yet it is often overlooked and stigmatized (Tuliao et al., 2020; Barete et al., 2023). Understanding and addressing mental health issues are fundamental to improving quality of life and fostering resilient communities.

Mental health issues among men represent a significant public health concern (Aperocho, 2023). Men are often socialized to suppress emotions and refrain from seeking help, which can exacerbate mental health problems (Agbayani et al., 2018). Young men, in particular, face unique challenges as they navigate the pressures of academic performance, career expectations, and social relationships during the formative period of their lives (Sato et al., 2022). This demographic is at a heightened risk for mental health issues, partly due to societal norms that discourage emotional vulnerability (Aruta et al., 2021). Men are often expected to exhibit stoicism and self-reliance, leading to underreporting of mental health issues and reluctance to seek help (Martinez et al., 2020). This cultural backdrop not only prevents men from accessing necessary mental health services but also perpetuates a cycle of silence and neglect (Hechanova & Regina, 2019).

A study investigating the mental health of male students aligns with the objectives outlined in Republic Act 11036, the Philippine Mental Health Law. The study examines the challenges and barriers students face in seeking help. Furthermore, understanding the mental health landscape for this demographic is crucial for effective planning and policy-making, ensuring resources are allocated strategically to meet the most pressing needs. This study addresses a significant empirical gap in the literature concerning young men's mental health (Bilsker et al., 2018; UNICEF, 2021). While numerous studies focus on general mental health concepts, there is a lack of research specifically targeting the unique experiences and challenges faced by men (Keynejad et al., 2021). This gap hinders the development of effective, evidence-based interventions that adequately support male students. By examining young men's mental health, this study seeks to add to the existing body of knowledge in the field.

The study aims to investigate the mental health experiences of male students, identifying the specific barriers and facilitators to mental health expression and help-seeking and illuminate the complex interplay between these factors and the mental health landscape for male students.

Research Questions

Mental health stigma remains a significant barrier to mental health expression and well-being among young men. Understanding the nuances of this stigma and its impact on mental health is crucial for developing effective interventions and support systems. This study aims to explore mental health expression and stigma experiences among male students. The study sought to answer the following

questions:

1. What are the levels of mental health among male students, considering:
 - 1.1. experiences in mental health expression; and
 - 1.2. perception of mental health stigma?
2. Is there a significant relationship between the students experience in mental health expression and perception of mental health stigma?
3. What are the subjective experiences of select male students regarding their mental health expression and stigma?
4. How are the quantitative levels of mental health expression and stigma associated with the qualitative experiences of male students?

Literature Review

Cultural norms and social environments can influence how men perceive and express concerns about their mental health. Open discussions about mental well-being may be discouraged, potentially leading to feelings of seclusion and a lack of support. Some societal attitudes and cultural beliefs may frame mental health challenges as weaknesses or personal failings (Kudva et al., 2020; Martinez et al., 2020; Tuliao et al., 2020). Studies suggest that the level of stigma persists, potentially influencing their willingness to seek help and discuss their mental health openly (Tuliao, 2021; Sato et al., 2022).

Furthermore, there is also a connection between social expectations and cultural ideas about masculinity and how men express their emotions. Some societal norms may emphasize emotional control, potentially leading to concerns about being judged or rejected for expressing vulnerability (Veissière, 2018; Butler, 2023; Harianti, 2023). This focus on emotional control may influence their readiness to share their experiences with mental health challenges, potentially contributing to the association between mental health and a lack of openness (Huggett et al., 2018; Martinez et al., 2020). Social expectations around masculinity can influence how men express emotions. Societal emphasis on emotional control and fear of judgment for vulnerability may lead men, particularly students, to be less open about mental health challenges. This dynamic contributes to the association between mental health and a lack of openness. Interventions that address these societal norms and create supportive environments are crucial. (Huggett et al., 2018; Veissière, 2018; Martinez et al., 2020; Butler, 2023; Harianti, 2023).

Negative social views of mental health can also discourage men from seeking help. When open communication is lacking, men may feel isolated and unheard. These experiences reflect broader societal attitudes that do not fully acknowledge the seriousness of mental health concerns. Interventions that challenge these opposing views and promote supportive environments are necessary. (Kudva et al., 2020; Tuliao et al., 2020; Aruta et al., 2021; Christiansen et al., 2021). Men navigate various challenges in managing their mental health. Strategies such as situational awareness and gradually engaging in discussions about mental health can be helpful for them. Efforts to address societal perceptions and raise awareness within the community can contribute to a more supportive environment (Tabudlo et al., 2022; Sasraatmadja et al., 2023). Peer support can also be valuable, offering a safe space for open communication and understanding (Carandang et al., 2020; World Health Organization, 2021).

Studies examining mental health stigma and expression in men highlight a complex interplay of cultural, societal, and individual factors. These factors can create challenges for men in openly discussing their mental health. Societal expectations of stoicism and traditional masculinity may be associated with a reluctance to talk about mental health concerns. This dynamic can contribute to a sense of isolation and potentially reinforce negative views of mental health (stigma). Relationships with peers and family may also influence how men express themselves, with experiences that minimize or dismiss concerns potentially adding to these challenges.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized an explanatory sequential research design (Toyon, 2021) that collected and analyzed quantitative data first, followed by qualitative data, to gain deeper insights. Initially, the study gathered quantitative data to measure the experiences of mental health expression and the levels of mental health stigma among male students. Following this, qualitative methods were employed to delve into these students detailed personal experiences and interpretations of mental health expression. The study was conducted within the college department of an institution in Malaybalay City, Bukidnon. This locale offers a unique cultural and educational context, which is crucial for understanding the specific challenges and perceptions related to mental health expression.

Participants, Instrument, and Procedure

Phase 1 – Quantitative Exploration

In the study's first phase, convenience sampling (Sedgwick, 2013) was employed to select participants. This sampling method was chosen for its practicality and efficiency in gathering many responses quickly. The study surveyed male students who were readily available and willing to participate. One hundred six (106) responses were recorded, providing a substantial sample for quantitative analysis.

Table 1. *Demographic profile of the survey respondents (N=106 males)*

Demographic Profile		f	%
Year	1st Year	32	30.2
	2nd Year	38	35.8
	3rd Year	27	25.5
	4th Year	4	3.8
	Special Year	5	4.7
Age	18-20	44	41.5
	21-23	56	52.8
	24-26	6	5.7

The study participants, as displayed in Table 1, includes a diverse sample of male students ranging from first to fourth year, with some categorized as special year students. These participants, aged 18 to 26, provide a broad representation of the student body, allowing for a comprehensive examination of mental health expression and stigma across different stages of their academic journey. This diverse age and academic range ensure that the study captures a wide array of experiences and perspectives, thereby enhancing the validity and reliability of the findings.

The first phase utilized two research instruments. The first was a researcher-made questionnaire patterned after the works of Feijó et al. (1997) and Tibubos et al. (2022), and three experts in the field validated the questionnaire (Boparai et al., 2018) and demonstrated high reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.854. The second instrument was an adopted questionnaire from Gierk et al. (2018), which also validated and exhibited strong reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.877.

Data was gathered through an online survey (Van Selm & Jankowski, 2006), ensuring voluntary participation and adherence to data privacy protocols. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study, their rights to confidentiality and anonymity, and their ability to withdraw at any time without consequence (Govil, 2013). The online format facilitated broad participation and efficient data collection, ensuring comprehensive coverage of the target population.

Phase 2 – Qualitative Exploration

In the second phase, maximum variation sampling (Coyne, 1997) was employed to select participants for qualitative interviews. This sampling technique was chosen to capture various perspectives and experiences regarding mental health expression and stigma. The study ensured a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon by selecting participants from various academic years and backgrounds. Five (5) participants were interviewed, with data saturation achieved by the fifth interview, indicating that no new significant information was emerging.

Table 2. *Demographic profile of the interview participant (N=5 males)*

Participant	Year	Age	Been Stigmatized	Avoided Help
M-1	4th year	23	Unsure	Yes
M-2	2nd year	22	Unsure	No
M-3	1st year	19	Yes	Yes
M-4	3rd year	21	Yes	Yes
M-5	2nd year	21	Yes	Yes

The interview portion of the study, as displayed in Table 2, includes five male participants, ranging in age from 19 to 23 and representing different academic years from first to fourth year. Among these participants, two were unsure if they had been stigmatized for expressing their mental health issues, while three had experienced stigma. Additionally, four out of the five participants had avoided seeking help for their mental health problems, highlighting a significant barrier to accessing support, while one participant had not avoided help.

The qualitative questionnaire used in this phase was developed based on the results of the quantitative analysis from the first phase. It was thoroughly validated and reviewed by five (5) experts in psychology, guidance and counseling, and psychometrics, all of whom are active in the field of education. The validation ensured that the interview questions were relevant, clear, and capable of eliciting rich, detailed participant responses (Boparai et al., 2018).

Data gathering involved conducting in-depth semi-structured interviews (Kallio et al., 2016), adhering to principles of confidentiality and anonymity, informed consent, voluntary participation, and the right to withdraw (Govil, 2013). The interviews were recorded with the participants' permission to ensure accuracy and lasted an average of 23 minutes, allowing for detailed and comprehensive discussions without causing the participants undue fatigue. The interviews were conducted in a safe and supportive environment, with an individual who is certified in psychological first-aid and mental health first-aid present to provide immediate support if needed.

Data Analysis

The study employed data cleaning (Ilyas & Che, 2019) as a crucial step in the analysis process. Initially, 113 responses were recorded,

but after thorough data cleaning, only 106 valid responses remained. Data cleaning was necessary to remove incomplete or inconsistent responses, ensuring the integrity and reliability of the dataset. As presented in Table 3 below, the Shapiro-Wilk test was performed for the experience on mental health expression ($W=0.872$, $p=0.052$) and mental health stigma ($W=0.839$, $p=0.057$) and did not show evidence of non-normality. Based on the result, the researchers opted to use the parametric test.

Table 3. Test for Normality (Shapiro-Wilk)

Variable	W	p
Experience in Mental Health Expression	0.872	0.052
Mental Health Stigma	0.839	0.057

Based on the result of Table 3, the analysis utilized descriptive statistics to characterize the baseline demographics of the respondents. Mean and standard deviation were employed to summarize the data, providing an overview of the student's experiences with mental health expression and the level of perceived mental health stigma. Correlation analysis was conducted to explore the relationship between these variables. The correlation analysis examined the strength and direction of the association between the students' self-reported mental health expression and their perception of mental health stigma.

For the qualitative data, the study utilized thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2012) following the frameworks of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) (Smith et al., 2015) and Critical Hermeneutics (Byrne, 2001). This approach allowed for an in-depth analysis of the interview data, focusing on the participants' personal experiences and interpretations of mental health expression. Thematic analysis streamlined the identification of key themes and patterns, while IPA provided a detailed examination of how participants made sense of their experiences. Critical Hermeneutics offered a broader socio-cultural and historical context, enriching the interpretation and providing deeper insights into the systemic aspects of mental health expression.

Results and Discussion

Experience on Mental Health Expression

Table 4 presents the mean score, standard deviation, and qualitative interpretation of the male students' experiences towards their mental health expression.

Table 4. College students experience on mental health expression (N=106 Males)

Mental Health Expression	<i>x</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>Q.I.</i>
Felt isolated after sharing problem to another person.	4.30	0.781	CE
Felt unheard by the other person when sharing problem to them.	4.25	0.774	CE
Felt discriminated for sharing mental health problem	4.25	0.802	CE
Think that sharing problems means losing their masculinity.	4.24	0.761	CE
Feel that the problem is not taken seriously because of being a man.	4.22	0.795	CE
Feel that the problem is taken lightly or a joke by the other person when sharing.	4.21	0.781	CE
Been judged when expressing emotions or sharing problems.	4.21	0.744	CE
Felt societal pressure not to share problems to the people around.	4.19	0.722	FE
Felt discouraged to speak regarding mental health problems.	4.07	0.768	FE
Avoided seeking help regarding mental health because of how it might negatively change the perception of people.	4.06	0.806	FE
Experienced hiding mental health problems in order to not appear weak or vulnerable to others.	4.01	0.783	FE
Felt the need to hide mental health problems in order to not to be judged by people.	3.94	0.763	FE
Felt that that there is no need to share problems to family, friends, etc.	3.94	0.774	FE
Overall	4.15	0.754	FE

Legend: CE – Constantly Experienced; OE – Occasionally Experienced; NE – Never Experienced; FE – Frequently Experienced; RE – Rarely Experienced

As presented in Table 4, among the 13 statements evaluated, the highest mean score was 4.30 ($SD=0.781$) for "Felt isolated after sharing problem to another person," with a qualitative interpretation of "constantly experienced." The results indicate that a significant number of male students frequently feel isolated after discussing their mental health issues, highlighting a critical barrier to open communication about mental health. The lowest mean scores, 3.94, were found for the statements "Felt the need to hide mental health problems in order to not to be judged by people" ($SD=0.763$) and "Felt that there is no need to share problems with family, friends, etc.," ($SD=0.774$) both interpreted as "frequently experienced." Overall, the experience of mental health expression had a mean score of 4.15 ($SD=0.754$), indicating that male students frequently encounter challenges when expressing their mental health concerns.

These findings posit that social interactions and cultural contexts shape our understanding and experiences (McKenzie et al., 2018; Cleofas, 2020). The high frequency of feeling isolated and the need to hide mental health issues suggest that the cultural and social environment may not be supportive or accepting of open mental health discussions (Huggett et al., 2018; Martinez et al., 2020; Christiansen et al., 2021). This social context can perpetuate stigma and create an environment where students feel unsafe or unsupported in sharing their mental health struggles, reinforcing the stigma associated with mental health expression (Tuliao et al., 2020; Bangalan & Agnes, 2024).

Level of Mental Health Stigma

Table 5 presents the mean score, standard deviation, and qualitative interpretation of the male students' level of mental health stigma.

Table 5. *College students' level of mental health stigma (N=106)*

<i>Mental Health Stigma</i>	<i>x</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>Q.I.</i>
I think that most people hesitate to entrust their child with someone who has been treated for a mental illness.	2.83	0.697	ML
I think that most people take the opinion of someone who has been treated for mental illness less seriously.	2.81	0.657	ML
I think that most people think badly of someone who has been treated for a mental illness.	2.75	0.689	ML
I think that most people do not enter into a relationship with someone who has been treated for a mental illness.	2.74	0.664	ML
I think that most people do not even take a look at an application from someone who has been treated for a mental illness.	2.70	0.628	ML
I think that most people hesitate to do business with someone who has been treated for a mental illness.	2.66	0.611	ML
I think that most people consider someone who has been treated for a mental illness to be dangerous.	2.65	0.637	ML
I think that most people feel uneasy when someone who has been treated for a mental illness moves into the neighborhood.	2.60	0.684	ML
I think that most people consider mental illness to be a sign of personal weakness.	2.60	0.633	ML
Overall	2.70	0.668	ML

Legend: HL – High Level of Stigma; MLL – Moderate-Low Level of Stigma; ML – Moderate Level of Stigma; LL – Low Level of Stigma

As presented in Table, the highest mean score, 2.83 (SD=0.697), was for the statement, "I think that most people hesitate to entrust their child with someone who has been treated for a mental illness," interpreted as a "moderate level of stigma." This result indicates a prevalent societal hesitation and distrust towards individuals with mental health issues. The lowest mean scores, 2.60, were for the statements "I think that most people feel uneasy when someone who has been treated for a mental illness moves into the neighborhood" (SD=0.684) and "I think that most people consider mental illness to be a sign of personal weakness," (SD=0.633) both also indicating a "moderate level of stigma." Overall, the level of mental health stigma had a mean score of 2.70 (SD=0.668), suggesting a moderate level of stigma among male students.

The findings highlight how societal attitudes and cultural beliefs contribute to the stigma surrounding mental health (Tuliao et al., 2020). The moderate level of stigma reflected in students' perceptions suggests that mental health issues are still primarily viewed through a lens of distrust and weakness (Tuliao, 2021; Sato et al., 2022). This societal construction of mental illness as a negative trait can influence students' willingness to seek help and openly discuss their mental health (Martinez et al., 2020), which perpetuates the stigma and barriers to adequate mental health support (Kudva et al., 2020; Taguibao & Rosenheck, 2021).

Relationship between Mental Health Expression and Mental Health Stigma

Table 6 presents the extent of association between the students experience regarding mental health expression and level of mental health stigma.

Table 6. *Relationship between mental health expression and mental health stigma*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>x</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>Ext. of Re.</i>	<i>p</i>
Mental Health Expression	4.15	0.729	Strong Positive Relationship	0.008**
Mental Health Stigma	2.70			

Note: ** $P < 0.01$

The results, as presented in Table 6, reveal the Pearson correlation analysis between the student's experience regarding mental health expression and the level of mental health stigma. The analysis exhibited a positive correlation between the two variables $r(103) = 0.729$, $p = 0.008$. This significant correlation indicates that constant negative experiences regarding mental health expression are associated with higher levels of mental health stigma among the male respondents. The strong relationship suggests that constant negative experiences with mental health expression may influence the level of mental health stigma.

The negative correlation underscores the impact of socially constructed stigma on individual behavior. The stigma associated with mental health creates a hostile environment where students are discouraged from discussing their mental health issues (Martinez et al., 2020; Tuliao, 2021). The construction of mental health as a stigmatized and undesirable trait inhibits open communication and expression, leading to a culture of silence and isolation (Huggett et al., 2018; Aruta et al., 2021; Christiansen et al., 2021). Understanding this relationship is crucial for developing interventions that address stigma and promote a more supportive environment for mental health expression.

Phenomenology on Mental Health Expression

Figure 1 presents the overview of the thematic chart on the subjective experience regarding mental health expression. Four (4) significant themes were generated: stereotyping, social dynamics, emotional state, and adaptive mechanisms. Per themes, sub-themes were also generated and recorded.

Figure 2. Thematic overview on the subjective experiences of the mental health expression of the select participants of the study

Stereotyping

The first sub-theme under *Stereotyping* on *Toxic Masculinity* articulated how societal norms surrounding masculinity inhibit their ability to express emotions, as underscored by the statements from the participants:

“...this toxic masculinity...when men express their feelings, it is interpreted as a sign of weakness...” (M-1)

“...a thing for me is that people really say that males are strong and we don't have the right to share about our feelings...” (M-5)

These statements reveal how the pervasive cultural narrative of toxic masculinity constrains male students' emotional expression, as they fear being perceived as weak (Butler, 2023; Harianti, 2023). The result highlights the subjective experience of male students who internalize societal expectations of stoicism, impacting their mental health by discouraging openness and vulnerability (Veissière, 2018; Cebreros, 2023). Moreover, the societal power structures perpetuating these harmful norms suggest that systemic change is necessary to dismantle these stereotypes (Barillas & Aguirre, 2024).

The second sub-theme under *Stereotyping* on *Emotional Weakness* captures the participants' fear of judgment and rejection, as reflected in statements like:

“...the fear of judgement and rejection from our peers because admitting vulnerability is a sign of weakness...” (M-3)

“...I often hesitate to talk about my struggles for fear of being seen as weak...” (M-4)

This fear indicates that emotional expression is often met with negative social consequences, reinforcing a culture of silence around mental health issues (Kudva et al., 2020). These experiences show how male students navigate their mental health within a social

context that equates vulnerability with weakness (Basilio, 2019). This subjective struggle highlights the need for supportive environments where emotional expression is normalized and validated. Moreover, these attitudes are not just individual beliefs but are rooted in broader societal and cultural norms that stigmatize emotional openness in men (Tuliao et al., 2020).

The third sub-theme under *Stereotyping on Gender Expectations* emphasizes the societal pressure for men to conform to traditional gender roles, as evidenced by statements such as:

“...there’s pressure for men to be tough and not show vulnerability.” (M-3)

“...one factor for me not to talk is that the perspective of society towards men, that men are strong and can handle everything...” (M-4)

These expectations create a rigid framework within which male students feel compelled to suppress their emotional needs (Tan, 2022). This result highlights how these gender expectations shape the personal experiences of male students, leading to internal conflicts and hindered mental health expression (Martinez et al., 2020; Villamor & Dy, 2022). Moreover, the role of societal structures and cultural narratives in maintaining these gender norms advocates for critically examining and transforming these pervasive ideologies (Tuliao et al., 2020).

These themes under *Stereotyping* highlight the subjective experiences of male students navigating their mental health within the context of societal expectations. The study highlights how participants internalize cultural constructs of masculinity that emphasize emotional suppression. These constructs often associate expressing emotions, particularly vulnerability or sadness, with weakness and a lack of masculinity. This pressure to suppress emotions can lead to isolation, difficulty connecting with others, and disconnecting from one's inner experience (Tan, 2022; Harianti, 2023). The analysis goes beyond biological determinism, recognizing the role of power dynamics and cultural narratives in shaping male experiences. Traditional gender roles often position men as dominant and unemotional figures (Tuliao et al., 2020). These narratives constrain how male students perceive and express their mental health concerns—fearing being ostracized or seen as less than a man can prevent them from seeking help or expressing vulnerability (Tuliao, 2021; Cebberos, 2023).

This internalized pressure to conform to rigid masculinity ideals creates a cycle of silence around mental health among male students. The inability to express emotions freely can exacerbate existing problems, leading to feelings of loneliness, frustration, and potentially worsening mental health. Furthermore, the lack of open conversation about mental health within the male community creates a sense of isolation and reinforces the idea that struggling is abnormal. Given the systemic nature of stereotypes and the deep-rooted societal norms that perpetuate them, addressing cultural and structural factors is crucial to fostering a more supportive environment for mental health expression among male students (Tuliao et al., 2020).

Social Dynamics

The first sub-theme under *Social Dynamics on Peer Dynamics* is illustrated by participants' experiences with insensitive jokes and comments about mental health. Statements such as:

“...I once had a classmate make a joke about depression, not knowing that I struggled with it. It made me feel really uncomfortable...” (M-3)

“...there are jokes that are very below the belt... I feel down when they joke about what I feel...” (M-5)

This result highlights the negative impact of peer behavior on mental health expression. These experiences emphasize male students' personal and emotional responses to peer interactions that trivialize their struggles (Javier et al., 2018; Hechanova & Regina, 2019). Moreover, these peer dynamics reflect broader societal attitudes that undermine the seriousness of mental health issues, perpetuating a culture where such concerns are not taken seriously (Kudva et al., 2021).

The second sub-theme under *Social Dynamics on Familial Dynamics* delves into the challenges male students face within their family environments. Participants shared experiences of feeling invalidated by family members, as seen in statements like:

“...I once told my mother that ‘I’m not feeling well’... she used the word ‘buang [crazy]’ to invalidate my feelings... I felt that my feelings and experiences were invalidated...” (M-1)

“...with family, it can be a bit trickier...like, they might not understand or they might worry too much...” (M-3)

“...that is why I do not share anymore with my family...they invalidate my feelings...they even stated that I am gay because I expressed what I feel...” (M-5)

The results highlight how these familial interactions shape the personal experiences of male students, contributing to a sense of isolation and reluctance to share their feelings (Javier et al., 2018; Tuliao et al., 2020). These dynamics are embedded within cultural norms and familial expectations that stigmatize mental health discussions, revealing a need for greater awareness and education within families to foster supportive environments (Hechanova & Regina, 2019; Taguibao & Rosenheck, 2021; Tuliao, 2021).

The third sub-theme under *Social Dynamics on Social Invalidation* addresses the broader societal responses to mental health expression. Participants noted experiences of dismissal and trivialization, such as:

“...for me, I might not be given any second thought. I’m not afraid to talk about my problems, but I had an experience, it was from a friend, I shared a problem and he just scoffed at it and changed the topic as if it didn’t matter...” (M-1)

“...I mean, there have been times when I’ve tried to bring it up, but they don’t really know how to respond...or they’ll just brush it off and say things like ‘just cheer up’, ‘laban lang [fight on]’, ‘just laugh it off’, or ‘it’s all in your head’... it can be frustrating sometimes...” (M-3)

These narratives reveal the profound personal impact of social invalidation, leading to frustration and a diminished willingness to discuss mental health issues (Aperocho, 2023). Moreover, these individual experiences are shaped by broader societal discourses that minimize and stigmatize mental health struggles, underscoring the need for cultural shifts to validate and support mental health expression (Tuliao et al., 2020; Aruta et al., 2021).

These themes under *Social Dynamics* reveal a complex interplay of societal attitudes that collectively hinder open mental health expression among male students. Which profoundly influences the mental health expression of male students. The study illuminates the lived experiences of stigma and invalidation faced by male students. This stigma can manifest in various ways, such as feeling dismissed, ridiculed, or misunderstood by friends, family, or healthcare professionals (Aperocho, 2023). These experiences can create feelings of shame, isolation, and hopelessness, further hindering help-seeking behavior.

However, the study goes beyond individual experiences, acknowledging the broader social and cultural contexts contributing to stigma (Tuliao et al., 2020). Traditional notions of masculinity often emphasize stoicism and strength, making expressions of vulnerability or mental health struggles seem incompatible. Additionally, cultural beliefs surrounding mental illness might contribute to stigma by viewing it as a weakness or a personal failing (Javier et al., 2018; Hechanova & Regina, 2019). These findings underscore the need for a multi-faceted approach to address mental health stigma and create a more supportive environment for male students.

Emotional State

The first sub-theme under *Emotional State on Social Anxiety* illustrates the discomfort and fear associated with discussing mental health issues. Participants reported feeling uneasy and apprehensive about communicating their mental health struggles, even with close family and friends. The participants shared:

“...I think I’m not so comfortable to discuss my mental health with my family and friends...I am also afraid to communicate with them...” (M-2)

“...I feel afraid, even when I trust the person, because the group might treat you differently once they know you have a mental health condition...” (M-3)

These statements highlight the deeply personal and subjective nature of social anxiety, showing how the anticipation of adverse reactions can inhibit open communication about mental health (Aruta et al., 2021; Tan, 2022).

The second sub-theme under *Emotional State on Fear of Judgement* further emphasizes the reluctance to express mental health issues due to concerns about being judged or stigmatized. Participants expressed a strong sense of vulnerability and the perceived risk of negative evaluations from others. One participant noted:

“...in all honesty, I am not comfortable talking about my mental health because I feel that I will be judged if I share my problems...” (M-4)

This fear of judgment underscores the internalized stigma that many male students experience, which can lead to self-censorship and a reluctance to seek help (Taguibao & Rosenheck, 2021). These experiences reveal how societal norms and cultural expectations contribute to the fear of being judged, thereby reinforcing the silence around mental health issues (Javier et al., 2018; Tuliao et al., 2020).

These themes under *Emotional State* capture male students' inner experiences and emotional challenges when expressing their mental health concerns. The result reveals a complex emotional landscape where social anxiety and fear of judgment intersect to create significant barriers to mental health expression among male students (Aruta et al., 2021). The study suggests that male students grapple with social anxiety when contemplating talking about their mental health. This social anxiety could manifest as worries about public scrutiny, fear of adverse reactions from peers, or a reluctance to appear weak or vulnerable (Tuliao et al., 2020). Social anxiety can lead to feelings of isolation and a sense of burden, further hindering help-seeking behavior (Javier et al., 2018).

Closely linked to social anxiety is the fear of judgment. Male students may be concerned about being labeled or stereotyped for experiencing mental health issues (Taguibao & Rosenheck, 2021). This fear could stem from societal norms associating masculinity with strength and stoicism, making expressions of vulnerability seem incongruent with those expectations. These themes are not isolated but operate in a complex interplay (Veissière, 2018; Harianti, 2023). Social anxiety might heighten the fear of judgment, making students even more apprehensive about expressing their needs. These combined emotions can create a significant barrier to seeking help, leading to feelings of loneliness and potentially worsening mental health problems. Addressing these emotional barriers is essential for enabling male students to feel more comfortable and supported in sharing their mental health experiences.

Adaptive Mechanisms

The first sub-theme under *Adaptive Mechanisms on Self-Coping* emphasizes individual strategies for managing mental health. One participant stated:

“...I think finding the right timing and approach is key... maybe starting with a casual conversation or bringing up a relevant news article or movie can help ease into it... and emphasizing that you just need someone to listen, not necessarily fix everything...” (M-3)

This statement underscores the personalized and context-sensitive nature of self-coping mechanisms, reflecting the importance of situational awareness and gradual engagement in mental health discussions (Tabudlo, 2022).

The second sub-theme under *Adaptive Mechanisms on Taking Action* involves proactive efforts to change perceptions and increase awareness about mental health. A participant highlighted:

“...I try to raise the awareness regarding mental health in the community to change the culture gradually... by promoting the idea that it's okay for men to seek help and talk about their emotions openly...” (M-3)

This statement reveals individuals' active role in challenging and reshaping societal norms, facilitating a societal transformation characterized by increased acceptance and transparency regarding mental health concerns (Sastratmadja et al., 2023).

The third sub-theme under *Adaptive Mechanisms on Peer Support* illustrates the reliance on friendships for emotional sharing and support. The participants mentioned:

“...I am more open about my mental health to my friends because they also experience the same as I do...” (M-1)

“...I'd rather share my problems to my friends because they understand what I feel...” (M-5)

These statements highlight the significance of shared experiences and mutual understanding among peers (Carandang et al., 2020; World Health Organization, 2021), which can create a supportive environment conducive to open communication about mental health (Tabudlo, 2022).

The fourth sub-theme under *Adaptive Mechanisms on Self-Care* focuses on personal practices that promote well-being. A participant expressed:

“...I'd rather go for a jog or take care of myself than worry... I watch that movie or eat that meal I've always wanted...” (M-2)

This statement emphasizes self-care as an essential coping strategy, reflecting a proactive approach to managing stress and enhancing mental health (Tabudlo, 2022).

These themes under *Adaptive Mechanisms* reveal a comprehensive approach to mental health expression, where self-coping, taking action, peer support, and self-care intersect to form a multifaceted strategy for managing mental health. The study emphasizes the importance of self-care as a foundational element of mental well-being. Self-care involves engaging in activities that promote physical and emotional health, such as exercise, healthy eating, relaxation techniques, and sleep hygiene. By prioritizing self-care, male students develop a proactive approach to managing stress and maintaining mental well-being (Tabudlo, 2022).

The research delves into the self-coping mechanisms employed by male students. These personalized strategies reflect a context-sensitive approach, where students adapt their coping mechanisms based on the situation. Developing situational awareness allows them to identify stressors and choose appropriate coping strategies, fostering resilience and emotional regulation (Agbayani et al., 2018). The findings highlight the crucial role of peer support in navigating mental health challenges (World Health Organization, 2021). Shared experiences and mutual understanding among peers can create a sense of belonging and decrease feelings of isolation. Peer support groups provide a safe space for open communication about mental health, where students can offer encouragement, empathy, and practical coping strategies (Carandang et al., 2020).

The study goes beyond individual strategies, exploring taking action (Sastratmadja et al., 2023). This theme emphasizes the importance of challenging and reshaping societal norms surrounding mental health. By advocating for change, male students can contribute to a cultural shift characterized by greater acceptance and openness regarding mental health concerns. This action-oriented approach empowers students to manage their mental health and create a more supportive environment for others. Addressing these adaptive mechanisms is essential for enabling male students to effectively manage their mental health and foster a culture of acceptance and support.

Linking Quantitative and Qualitative Findings on Mental Health Expression among Male Students

The qualitative results reveal a complex interplay between societal norms, personal experiences, and coping mechanisms that profoundly shape mental health expression among male students. The themes of stereotyping, social dynamics, emotional state, and adaptive mechanisms highlight how traditional notions of masculinity and societal attitudes toward mental health create significant barriers to open communication and support (Aruta et al., 2021). Male students internalize these cultural constructs, leading to a pervasive sense of isolation, fear of judgment, and reluctance to seek help (McKenzie et al., 2018; Tuliao et al., 2020; Taguibao &

Rosenheck, 2021). These qualitative insights provide understanding of the emotional and psychological landscape that male students navigate, which aligns with the quantitative findings that suggest a high frequency of feelings of isolation and the need to hide mental health issues (Martinez et al., 2020).

The quantitative results indicate that the cultural and social environment is often not supportive of open mental health discussions, perpetuating stigma and creating a hostile environment for students (Christiansen et al., 2021). This societal construction of mental illness as a negative trait influences students' willingness to seek help and openly discuss their mental health, reinforcing the stigma associated with mental health expression (Sato et al., 2022). The moderate level of stigma reflected in students' perceptions indicates that mental health issues are still viewed through a lens of distrust and weakness, which is corroborated by the qualitative findings that show how societal norms and cultural expectations contribute to the fear of being judged and the pressure to conform to traditional gender roles (Kudva et al., 2020; Tuliao, 2021).

The negative correlation between negative experiences regarding mental health expression and higher levels of mental health stigma underscores the impact of socially constructed stigma on individual behavior (Huggett et al., 2018). The qualitative data illustrate how negative peer dynamics, familial invalidation, and societal responses to mental health issues create an environment where students feel unsafe or unsupported in sharing their struggles (Javier et al., 2018; Aperocho, 2023). This hostile environment inhibits open communication and expression, leading to a culture of silence and isolation (Hechanova & Regina, 2019). Addressing these cultural and structural factors is crucial for developing interventions that promote a more supportive environment for mental health expression, thereby reducing stigma and encouraging help-seeking behavior among male students (World Health Organization, 2021).

Conclusions

The result highlights the critical need for interventions addressing individual and systemic mental health expression barriers. The combination of internal struggles and external invalidations creates a significant impediment to open discussions about mental health among male students. However, the adaptive mechanisms they employ suggest potential pathways for positive change. The study underscores the importance of creating supportive environments that validate and prioritize mental health. Promoting awareness, encouraging open discussions, and fostering inclusive and supportive social contexts are essential steps towards enabling male students to express their mental health experiences freely and confidently. Addressing the multifaceted challenges surrounding mental health expression requires a comprehensive strategy that tackles individual needs (through support systems) and broader societal issues (through education and cultural shifts) to create a truly inclusive and supportive environment.

Based on the results, several recommendations can be generated to improve mental health expression among male students. Firstly, there is a need for targeted educational programs that challenge traditional notions of masculinity and promote a more inclusive understanding of mental health. These programs could aim to reduce stigma by fostering a culture that views mental health struggles as an ordinary human experience rather than a sign of weakness. Secondly, institutions could establish and promote accessible mental health support services that are specifically designed to be welcoming to male students. Peer support networks and mental health awareness campaigns can play a crucial role in normalizing discussions about mental health.

Thirdly, family involvement in mental health education is essential to mitigate the invalidation and misunderstanding often experienced by students. Encouraging open communication within families and providing resources for parents to understand and support their children's mental health can create a more supportive home environment. Lastly, broader societal changes are necessary, including media campaigns and policy initiatives, to shift public perceptions and reduce the stigma associated with mental health issues. These multi-faceted approaches are vital for creating an environment where male students feel safe, supported, and encouraged to seek help and openly discuss their mental health challenges.

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